

Title of the Research Plan

1 Aim and objectives

1.1 Significance of research project in relation to current knowledge, research based starting points:

1.2 Research questions and/or hypotheses:

1.3 Expected research results and their anticipated scientific impact, potential for scientific breakthroughs and for promoting scientific renewal:

1.4 Special objective of call:

2 Implementation

2.1 Work plan and schedule:

2.2 Research data and material, methods, and research environment:

2.3 Risk assessment and alternative implementation strategies:

2.4 Added value of consortium (if the application is a consortium application):

3 Applicant, research team and collaborators

3.1 Project personnel and their project relevant key merits:

3.2 Collaborators:

4 Responsible science

4.1 Research ethics, equality and nondiscrimination, open science, and sustainable development:

5 Societal effects and impact

5.1 Effects and impact beyond academia:

6 Relevance to wider strategies, goals and objectives

6.1 Outline the relevance of the research project with regional, national and/or international strategies, goals and objectives.

6.2 Outline the relevance of the research project with HAMK's research strategy, goals, and objectives.

7 Planned research funding

7.1 Describe how you plan on funding your research and from which research funding institutions.

8 References

Maximum length